

**glycan
trigger**

D3.1 – Identification of the mechanism by which mucosa glycosylation switch regulates ILC-dependent immune response at gut mucosa

WP3

Date: 07 04 2025

Funded by
the European Union

DOCUMENT CONTROL SHEET

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project Number	101093997		
Project Acronym	GlycanTrigger		
Project Full title	Glycans as master triggers of health to intestinal inflammation transition		
Project Start Date	1 January 2023		
Project Duration	72 months		
Funding Instrument	Horizon Europe	Funding Scheme	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Topic	HORIZON-HLTH-2022-STAYHLTH-02-01		
Coordinator	Salomé Pinho (i3S), salomep@i3s.up.pt		

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Deliverable No 1.1	
Deliverable Title	Identification of the mechanism by which mucosa glycosylation switch regulates ILC-dependent immune response at gut mucosa
Work-Package No	WP3
Work-Package Title	Unravelling the cellular and molecular mechanisms of how changes in gut glycosylation activate innate and humoral immune responses
WP-Leader (Name and Short Org. Name)	Salomé Pinho (i3S)
Task No	3.1
Task Title	Task 3.1. The innate lymphoid cells axis triggered by changes in mucosa glycosylation associated with inflammation initiation
Task Leader (Name and Short Org. Name)	Andreas Diefenbach (CHARITE)
Main Author (Name and Short Org. Name)	Joana Gaifem (i3S); Andreas Diefenbach (CHARITE)
Other Authors (Name and Short Org. Name)	Vanda Pinto (i3S); Salomé Pinho (i3S)
Reviewers (Name and Short Org. Name)	Vanda Pinto (i3S); Salomé Pinho (i3S); Andreas Diefenbach (CHARITE)
Status	Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Final <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Deliverable Type	Report <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Data <input type="checkbox"/> Demonstration <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/>
Dissemination Level	Public (PU) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sensitive (SEN) <input type="checkbox"/> Classified <input type="checkbox"/> PU: Public, fully open SEN: Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444 Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444 Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

DOCUMENT VERSION HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description of Change
1	10/03/2025	Joana Gaifem (i3S)	Development of the first draft
2	20/03/2025	Vanda Pinto (i3S)	Prepared the 2 nd draft: editorial corrections. Included the Executive Summary
3	24/03/2025	Salomé Pinho (i3S)	Additional edits and Revision
4	03/04/2025	Andreas Diefenbach (CHARITE)	Additional edits and Revision
5	07/04/2025	Vanda Pinto (i3S)	Preparation of the final version

DOCUMENT REVIEW

Reviewer	Date	Reviewer Name (Short Organisation Name)
1	20/03/2025	Vanda Pinto (i3S)
2	24/03/2025	Salomé Pinho (i3S)
3	03/04/2025	Andreas Diefenbach (CHARITE)

Legal disclaimer

This project is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement no. 101093997. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CD	Crohn's Disease
CCR	C-C Chemokine Receptor
DSS	Dextran sulfate sodium
FACS	Fluorescence-Activated Cell Sorting
GlcNAc	N-Acetylglucosamine
GnT-V	N-Acetylglucosaminyltransferase V
IBD	Inflammatory Bowel Disease
ILC	Innate Lymphoid Cells
LTi	Lymphoid Tissue Inducer Cells
NCR	Natural Cytotoxicity Receptor
ROR	Retinoic Acid-Related Orphan Receptor
Th17	T Helper 17 Cells
UC	Ulcerative Colitis

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About the project

GlycanTrigger is a project funded by the European Union, within the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions (RIA). The long-term goal of GlycanTrigger is to unlock a new checkpoint that regulates health to chronic inflammation transition by proposing mucosa glycans modifications as a master switch towards the early perturbation of host-microbial interactions and the consequent activation of both innate and humoral immune systems. Ultimately, we want to intercept or revert this master switch and thereby exploit/analyse whether this constitutes an opportunity to prevent the development of chronic inflammation in at-risk individuals.

Chronic inflammation is the underlying cause of numerous diseases, including Crohn's disease (CD), which may have a preclinical phase with immunological changes occurring before symptoms manifest. To improve disease prediction and prevention, our innovative approach seeks to understand the health-to-intestinal inflammation transition using CD as a disease model. The GlycanTrigger project will investigate when, why and how changes in glycosylation at the surface of the gut mucosa, constitute an early trigger of the health-to-inflammation transition. We will address how changes in glycosylation of the gut mucosa act as a primary event that dysregulates not only local mechanisms, but also systemic mechanisms associated with health to inflammation transition. Although high-risk/high-gain, our project is based on appropriate and long-standing expertise and fundamental biological principles that the consortium has helped establish and is thus likely to lead to (i) breakthrough biomedical concepts in the driving factors that trigger the health to chronic inflammation transition and to (ii) novel predictive tools for early detection of at-risk individuals to develop chronic inflammation, as well as to (iii) a novel intervention strategy that will be tested for disease prevention. In the longer term, the results of GlycanTrigger will improve health literacy through better-informed management of health status, diet and life-style to maintain a healthy gut. Our strategy for understanding the transition from health to gut inflammation is comprehensive and includes the impact of mucosa glycans on local and systemic mechanisms.

Partners:

Number	Short Name	Legal Name
1	I3S (Coordinator)	I3S - INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACAO E INOVACAO EM SAUDE DA UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO (Portugal)
2	LUMC	ACADEMISCH ZIEKENHUIS LEIDEN (The Netherlands)
3	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITÉ (France)
4	CHARITE	CHARITE - UNIVERSITAETSMEDIZIN BERLIN (Germany)
5	GLSMED LH	GLSMED LEARNING HEALTH SA (Portugal)
5.1	HLL	HOSPITAL DA LUZ SA (Portugal)
6	MOUNT SINAI	ICAHN SCHOOL OF MEDICINE AT MOUNT SINAI (USA)
7	EFCCA	EUROPEAN FEDERATION OF CROHN'S AND ULCERATIVE COLITIS ASSOCIATIONS (Belgium)
8	SPI	SOCIEDADE PORTUGUESA DE INOVACÃO CONSULTADORIA EMPRESARIAL E FOMENTO DA INOVACÃO SA (Portugal)
9	LUD	LUDGER LIMITED (United Kingdom)

Executive Summary

Deliverable 3.1 outlines the findings from Work Package 3 (WP3) of the GlycanTrigger project, focusing on Task 3.1 titled, “***The innate lymphoid cells axis triggered by changes in mucosa glycosylation associated with inflammation initiation***”.

Using specific glycoengineered mouse models, we here explored the role of host epithelial glycosylation in modulating innate lymphoid cell (ILC) populations and its potential involvement in the transition from health-to-disease in inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). Our findings uncover a novel mechanism in gut immunity, demonstrating that mucosal N-glycans play a key role in regulating the immune responses of ILC3/ILC1 cells. These results establish mucosal glycosylation as an important factor in gut immunity and highlight its potential as a target for therapeutic strategies aimed at managing the health-to-disease transition in IBD.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1. Introduction

Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD) is a complex inflammatory disorder with a considerably high disease burden worldwide.[1] Comprising both Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC), IBD poses significant challenges to medical intervention due to the lack of information regarding the events leading to its pathology, thereby hampering the development of effective therapies.[2-4] Although the exact aetiology of IBD remains elusive, impairments in the intricate interaction between gut microbiota composition and host immune response have been identified as important contributors to disease onset.[2-4]

The intestinal epithelial barrier plays a crucial role in preventing excessive contact between microbial populations and the immune system.[5] A finely tuned balance between microbiota, the immune system, and barrier function is essential for proper intestinal function and maintaining homeostasis. However, disruptions in one or more of these components can lead to functional imbalances, ultimately triggering intestinal inflammation.[6]

Glycans play a crucial role in fine-tuning immune regulation both in homeostasis and in major diseases such as IBD and colorectal cancer. The specific influence of glycans on mucosal T cell activity and function has been demonstrated in IBD. Our research has shown that mucosal T lymphocytes from UC patients exhibit a deficiency in branched *N*-glycosylation, which correlates with disease severity.[7] Notably, *ex vivo* supplementation of mucosa T cells with *N*-acetylglucosamine (GlcNAc) enhanced branched *N*-glycosylation in the T cell receptor (TCR), suppressing proinflammatory responses and regulating T cell activity associated with disease control.[8] Additionally, we observed that *Mgat5*-deficient mice (lacking the enzyme *N*-acetylglucosaminyltransferase V (GnT-V), which is responsible for branched *N*-glycan synthesis) exhibited increased susceptibility to severe colitis. Treatment of *Mgat5* KO mice with GlcNAc was able to regulate the intestinal T cell-mediated immune response, associated with decreased disease severity, and suppression of disease progression.[8] These data highlight the importance of mucosa glycans in regulating immune response, although the impact on other essential immune populations, such as innate lymphoid cells (ILC), remains to be explored.

Taking advantage of glycoengineered mouse models, we here explored whether host epithelial glycosylation shapes ILC populations and how this can be at the basis of health-to-disease transition in IBD.

Chapter 2

Methods

2. Methods

2.1 Animals

C57BL/6 wild-type (*Mgat5^{WT}*) and *Mgat5*-deficient mice (*Mgat5^{-/-}*) were bred and maintained in accredited animal facilities at the Institute for Research and Innovation in Health (i3S). Mice were housed in groups of 5-10, in HEPA filter-bearing cages, under 12-hour light/dark cycles. Autoclaved chow and water were provided *ad libitum*. Females between 9 and 14 weeks were used. Experiments were conducted with the approval of the Animal Ethics Committee and the Animal Welfare Body of the i3S. The protocols are in agreement with in-house standards and rules for animal experimentation, comply with national legislation and are integrated within a project, which is licensed by the Portuguese competent authority – DGAV (license number 009268/2022-06-02).

2.2 DSS-induced colitis

Mice with 9 to 11 weeks of age were given dextran sulphate sodium (DSS; 2% (w/v), molecular weight approximately 36,000–50,000 Da; MP Biomedicals) in the drinking water *ad libitum* for 7 days. Clinical signs of colitis, such as weight loss, stool consistency, and presence of blood were monitored daily and measured by the disease activity index. Mice were euthanized at the end of each experiment, or earlier if the symptoms of clinical disease reached one of these endpoints: more than 20% weight loss, diarrhoea, or gross bleeding.

2.3 Isolation of lamina propria leukocytes

Colons were flushed with Ca- and Mg-free PBS. Fragments of 0.5-1 cm were incubated in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 10% foetal bovine serum (FBS), 1% penicillin/streptomycin, 1 mM CaCl₂, 1 mM MgCl₂, and 1 mg/mL of collagenase IV (Sigma), under 100 rpm agitation at 37°C for 40 minutes. Tissues were dissociated and filtered through a 70 µm cell strainer (BD Biosciences). Cell suspension was centrifuged, the pellet was resuspended in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 10% FBS, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin, and layered upon lymphoprep solution in a proportion of 1:2 (lymphoprep:cell suspension). After gradient centrifugation at 800 g for 20 minutes at 20°C (without acceleration or break), cells retained in the interface were collected for the staining of immune cells, whereas cells retained in the bottom of the tube were collected for staining of nonimmune cells. Both fractions were washed in RPMI and kept in ice before analysis.

To isolate lamina propria leukocytes from human fresh colonic biopsies, a mechanical dissociation was performed in HBSS with 1% Pen/Strep and 0.1% Gentamycin. Human fresh colonic biopsies were digested with 0.9 mg/mL of collagenase IV in RPMI supplemented with 10% FBS, 100 U/mL Pen/Strep, 1

mM CaCl₂ and 1 mM MgCl₂, for 45 min with agitation, at 37°C. Cell suspensions were then filtered in 70 µm cell strainers and washed with PBS. Following, cells were centrifuged for 10 min at 300 g and 4°C, and the pellet was resuspended in FACS buffer and ready to proceed for flow cytometry staining.

2.4 Flow cytometry analysis

All cells analysed by flow cytometry were stained with Fixable Viability Dye (FVD) eFluor™ 780 for viability analysis and exclusion of dead cells. For staining of lamina propria lymphocytes, cells were stimulated with 20 ng/mL of phorbol myristate acetate (PMA), 200 ng/mL ionomycin calcium salt, and 10 µg/mL of brefeldin A for 4 hours at 37°C. After staining with FVD, surface staining was performed by incubation for 30 minutes at 4°C with surface antibodies. Intracellular staining was performed using the eBioscience Foxp3/Transcription Factor Staining Buffer set and intracellular antibodies. Cells analysis was performed on a BD FACSCanto II (Becton Dickinson) or Cytex Aurora (Cytex). Data was analysed using FlowJo software (Tree Star).

2.5 Cytokine quantification

For the colon explants, cytokine concentrations were analysed by flow cytometry using cytometric bead arrays: the LEGENDplex™ MU Th Cytokine Panel (13-plex) (Biolegend), according to the manufacturer's instructions. Samples were measured on the BD Accuri C6 instrument (BD Biosciences, US) using a specific template provided by BD Biosciences.

Chapter 3

Results

3. Results

3.1 Impaired β 1,6-GlcNAc complex branched *N*-glycosylation leads to a downregulation of ILC3-IL-22 mediated immune response in the gut

Considering the role of gut mucosa *N*-glycans in intestinal inflammation and colitis severity, we investigated their mechanistic influence on intestinal inflammatory pathways. We observed that *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice, at steady-state, exhibited a significant downregulation of type 3 innate lymphoid cells (ILC3) in the colonic mucosa, when compared to *Mgat5*^{WT} mice (Figure 1A). This reduction persisted following colitis induction (Figure 2A). Among ILC3 subpopulations, the deficiency in complex branched *N*-glycans specifically affected CCR6⁻NCR⁻ROR γ t⁺ and CCR6⁺ILC3 (LTi-like) cells at baseline (Figure 1B-C), while NCR⁺ROR γ t⁺ ILC3 remained unaffected (Figure 1D).

Following disease induction, ILC3 expression was found to be decreased, particularly within the CCR6⁺ILC3 (LTi-like) subpopulation (Figure 2B). Additionally, IL-22 production by ILC3 at baseline was significantly reduced in *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice (Figures 1E-F), and this reduction persisted upon colitis induction (Figure 2C-D). Importantly, IL-22 production by Th17 cells remained unchanged at both baseline (Figure 1G-I) and after disease induction (Figure 2E-G), suggesting a specific impact of host glycosylation on the ILC3-IL22 axis.

Figure 1 Deficiency in mucosa β 1,6-GlcNAc complex branched N-glycosylation leads to an impaired ILC3-IL-22-mediated immune response at steady-state.

Frequency of (A) ILC3, (B) CCR6⁻NCR⁻ROR γ t⁺ ILC3, (C) CCR6⁺ILC3 (LTI-like) and (D) NCR⁺ROR γ t⁺ subsets in CD45⁺ cell population in *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice, at steady state. (E) Frequency of IL-22-producing ILC3 and (F) mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) of intracellular IL-22 in ILC3 of *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice at steady state. Frequency of (G) Th17 in CD45⁺ cell population, (H) IL-22-producing Th17 and (I) mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) of intracellular IL-22 in Th17 in *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice, at steady state. Frequency of (J) CD127⁺ILC1, and (K) ex-ILC3/ILC1-like cell subsets in CD45⁺ cell population in *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice, at steady state. (L-O) Cytokine concentrations in supernatants of colonic explants cultured for 24 hours. Concentrations are normalized to tissue weight. (P) The mRNA expression levels at steady state of gene encoding for *Il22ra2* in the colonic tissue measured by RT-qPCR. Expression of target gene mRNA was calculated based on housekeeping gene (*Gapdh*). mRNA expression levels were normalized for the average of mRNA levels of *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice. Each datapoint represents an

individual animal. Data is represented as mean \pm SD. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; **** $p < 0.0001$ using an unpaired two-tailed Student's t-test or Mann–Whitney test.

3.2 Alterations in host mucosa glycosylation promote the trans-differentiation of ILC3 into ILC1 phenotype.

Innate lymphoid cells (ILCs) exhibit remarkable plasticity, adapting their phenotype and function in response to environmental cues such as dietary and microbial signals [9]. The ILC3/ILC1 balance is crucial for gut homeostasis, with disruptions linked to intestinal inflammation, including IBD. However, the impact of host glycocalyx alterations on this balance remains unexplored. Our findings demonstrate a direct interplay between changes in mucosal *N*-glycosylation and ILC activity. Specifically, *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice showed enhanced trans-differentiation of ILC3 into an ILC1-like phenotype (Figure 1J), evidenced by an increase in ex-ILC3/ILC1-like cells (Figure 1K). A similar trend for increase in ILC1-like phenotype was observed in *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice after DSS-induced colitis (Figure 2H).

The proinflammatory environment induced by ILC3/ILC1 plasticity was further corroborated by increased TNF α and IL-6 production in colonic explants from *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice at baseline (Figure 1L-M) and after colitis induction (Figure 2I-J). Additionally, anti-inflammatory IL-10 levels were reduced at baseline (Figure 1N), although no significant differences were observed between *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice and *Mgat5*^{WT} mice post-colitis induction (Figure 2K). Similarly, IL-22 production in colonic explants remained unchanged at both baseline and post-induction (Figure 1O; Figure 2L). However, impaired IL-22 signaling in *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice was supported by increased expression of *Il22ra2*, encoding IL-22 binding protein (IL-22BP), a key inhibitor of IL-22 activity (Figure 1P).

Figure 2 Deficiency in mucosa β 1,6-GlcNAc complex branched *N*-glycosylation leads to an impaired ILC3-IL-22-mediated immune response upon DSS-induced colitis.

Frequency of (A) ILC3, as well as (B) CCR6-NCR-ROR γ t⁺ ILC3 subset in CD45⁺ cell population in *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice, upon DSS-induced colitis. (C) Frequency of IL-22-producing ILC3 and (D) mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) of intracellular IL-22 in ILC3 of *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice upon DSS-induced colitis. Frequency of (E) Th17 in CD45⁺ cell population, (F) IL-22-producing Th17 and (G) mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) of intracellular IL-22 in Th17 in *Mgat5*^{WT} and *Mgat5*^{-/-} mice. (I-L) Cytokine concentrations in supernatants of colonic explants cultured for 24 hours. Concentrations are normalized to tissue weight. Each datapoint represents an individual animal. Data is represented as mean \pm SD. **p* < 0.05; ***p* < 0.01 using an unpaired two-tailed Student's *t*-test or Mann-Whitney test.

These results provide novel evidence that alterations in mucosal *N*-glycosylation directly regulate an important intestinal homeostatic module mediated by ILCs, associated with ILC3 trans-differentiation into an ILC1-mediated proinflammatory phenotype. This finding aligns with previous reports of ILC3-to-ILC1 transition in inflamed mucosal biopsies from Crohn's disease patients, linked to anti-GM-CSF autoantibodies targeting glycosylation.[10] Overall, we have shown that deficiency in complex branched *N*-glycans at gut mucosa surface leads to a clear pro-inflammatory microenvironment, driven by ILC3/ILC1 module with a concomitant increased expression of TNF and IL-6 and the downregulation of IL-10. This further supports the biological relevance of mucosal glycosylation in the overall reprogramming of the pro-

inflammatory environment in the intestine. These evidences were published by Rodrigues & Gaifem et al.[11]

Chapter 4

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4. References

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Chapter 5

Final Remarks

5. Final Remarks

Our results revealed a new mechanism in gut immunity by demonstrating the ability of host mucosa N-glycans to regulate ILC3/ILC1 immune responses. These data highlight host mucosal glycosylation as an important determinant of gut immune response in homeostasis and disease bringing the relevance of host mucosa glycans and ILC axis in gut immunity associated with health to disease transition. The specific mechanisms by which mucosa glycosylation dictates ILC-associated immunity in the context of IBD will be further explored. The dynamics between gut immunity, in particular ILC populations, and intestinal microbiota composition, imposed by intestinal epithelial glycosylation will also be integrated in the subsequent steps of the project. Overall, this will contribute to a better understanding of the sequence of events associated with health-to-inflammation transition, aiming to pinpoint glycans as novel therapeutic targets for IBD prevention.

